

PERFORATION / TEARING OF THE EAR CURTAIN - CAUSES, SYMPTOMS, TREATMENT

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6082348>

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Abstract: *The eardrum (eardrum) is the membrane that separates the outer ear from the middle ear. The main function of this structure is to transmit sound. It is the first ring in the sound transmission chain. The tympanic membrane allows the transmission of sound vibrations along the auditory bones to deeper parts of the auditory system without compromising quality.*

Key words: *eardrum, tympanic membrane, Perforation, Drum curtain*

Perforation of the eardrum:

Perforation or rupture of the eardrum poses a risk of temporary or irreversible hearing loss, infection of the middle ear, or incorrect or only partial erosion of the eardrum. Violation of the integrity of the eardrum significantly reduces the quality of life. Therefore, the complications of this condition are serious enough.

The prognosis of hearing restoration in this case depends on the causes of the condition, the degree of perforation, and the therapeutic measures indicated.

CAUSES OF EAR CURTAIN PERFECTION

Drum curtain perforation is most common in the following cases:

Purulent course of ear infections - exudative pressure, accompanied by purulent dissolution of the eardrum, leads to its thinning and rupture;

A sharp drop in ambient pressure - when flying in air transport or hitting the ear with a palm (slap, slap) or any flat object;

Noisy injury;

Mechanical damage to the ear canal is when foreign objects enter or the ear is cleaned.

SYMPTOMS

Perforation of the eardrum is often accompanied by severe pain. You can also add the following characters:

Noise in the ear (tinnitus);

Decreased hearing;

Hearing ambient sounds and speech disorders;

Clear fluid, blood or pus flowing from the ear;

Nausea and vomiting that cause dizziness;

If the perforation is due to excessive internal pressure of the exudate, the pain will be reduced as a result of the excess pus coming out after the perforation.

WHAT TO DO IF THE EAR CURTAIN IS PERFECTED: TREATMENT

In some cases (according to statistics, 55%) the ruptured eardrum is repaired independently without any intervention. Discharge occurs naturally, as does any injury to the body. In severe clinical cases, surgery may be required (meringoplasty and tympanoplasty). If the injury is very large or if a serious long-term purulent process interferes with the natural restoration of the integrity of the membrane, surgical intervention is required.

The operation can be performed under general or local anesthesia. If material is needed to close the hole, the skin on the ear canal is often removed. The manipulation is performed under microscopic control using micro-instruments and self-absorbing sutures.

Postoperative rehabilitation may require wearing a tampon soaked in an antibiotic solution inside the ear. There are also a number of recommendations that should be strictly followed during the recovery period:

It is not possible to sniff the nose sharply;

Intensive nasal breathing and other actions that increase pressure in the middle ear are prohibited;

Swimming is not recommended. Care should be taken not to drop fluid into the ear;

It is also recommended to refrain from traveling by air;

Prophylactic measures should be taken to prevent infectious diseases of the ENT organs.

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